

replication. A rubber dehusker was used to dehull the grain.

The HKRs (husk weight divided by kernel weight) of a variety in transplanted aman and boro seasons were similar but numerically higher than those in

transplanted aus, which had comparatively lower spikelet fills.

Clear HKR differences occurred in the five varieties. HKR variation was wide and environmental coefficient of variability was low in all seasons, indicating that HKR

is less responsive to environmental factors. Heritability for HKR was high; genetic advance was more or less similar in the three seasons. HKR may be a nearly stable indicator in screening for cultivars with lower husk content. □

Lectins in living organisms interact with silicon

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An unspecified interaction of lectins with silicon compounds exists in the tissues of silicophiles, both in living organisms and in histological preparations. Scientists need to consider this phenomenon when they use lectins, immunochemicals, and their dyes in silicophile studies.

Lectin preparations (including stains) were previously considered to interact specifically with sugars or their residues.

Silica structures of the rice husk of Krasnodarsky 424. Microspodography × 20

We have shown that during rice husk microspodography the lectins interact actively with silicon compounds that are present in large amounts in silicophile tissues (see figure). Silica can comprise up to 20% of some rice tissue dry matter.

Attention to this may prevent erroneous conclusions that interactions were with sugars rather than with silicon compounds. □

Grain quality

Grain quality of F₁ rice hybrids

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Nine rice hybrids developed at RARS and check cultivar Jaya were evaluated for physicochemical and cooked rice characteristics. Standard methods were used to analyze dried grain with about 12% moisture content. Recovery varied from 78 to 80% for hulling and from 72.5 to 75.5% for milling. Five of the hybrids

showed significantly higher head rice recovery than Jaya (RHR1, RHR4, RHR6, RHR7, and RHR9). The rest (except RHR5) were statistically at par with Jaya (see table). Head rice recovery was very high, which suggests undermilling of rice by a Kett Polisher (model TP 20).

Physicochemical characters of F₁ rice hybrids^a at RARS, R. S. Pura, India.

Hybrid or variety	Cross combination	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)	Head rice (%)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	L/W ratio	Abdominal white ^b	Alkali spreading value	Water uptake (%)	Volume expansion ratio	Elongation ratio	Amylose (%)
RHR1	Zhen Shan 97 A/IR3 1868	80.0	75.0	73.5	5.60	2.27	2.47	OP	2.0	165	3.7	1.7	19.2
RHR2	V20 A/IR31802	78.0	73.0	68.5	6.65	2.26	2.94	Present	2.0	160	4.0	1.5	17.0
RHR3	Zhen Shan 97 A/IR8585	78.0	72.5	70.0	5.84	2.41	2.42	Present	4.0	170	3.7	1.6	17.0
RHR4	Zhen Shan 97 A/IR31802	78.5	75.5	72.0	5.67	2.36	2.40	Absent	2.0	150	3.7	1.7	17.0
RHR5	Zhen Shan 97 A/IET1410	78.0	73.5	68.0	6.98	1.99	3.51	Absent	6.0	350	3.7	1.5	20.3
RHR6	Zhen Shan 97 A/VL 15	79.5	74.5	70.5	5.66	2.71	2.09	Present	3.0	200	3.7	1.4	20.9
RHR7	VA20 A/IR3 1851	79.5	74.0	71.0	6.59	2.34	2.82	Present	3.0	140	3.7	1.5	17.5
RHR8	IR48483 A/IR83619	78.0	73.0	69.5	6.14	2.39	2.57	OP	3.0	150	3.7	1.6	16.0
RHR9	IR46830 A/IR36	79.0	74.0	71.0	6.62	2.09	3.17	Absent	2.0	140	3.7	1.5	19.2
Jaya	Check	79.0	74.5	69.0	6.37	2.57	2.48	Present	7.0	350	4.0	1.7	29.6
	LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.7	1.2	0.36	0.14	—	—	1.3	59	0.7	0.1	2.70

^aAv of 2 replications. ^bOP = occasionally present.

Length/width ratio of the milled grain ranged from 2.09 to 3.51. All hybrids except RHR5 and RHR9 displayed some degree of abdominal white. Volume

expansion ratio and elongation ratio after cooking of hybrids were statistically at par with or significantly inferior to Jaya. Water uptake values of all hybrids,

except RHR5 (alkali spreading value 6), were significantly lower than that of Jaya.

Amylose content was 16–20.9% for hybrids and 29.6% for Jaya. □

Relationship among grain shape, size, and head rice recovery (HRR) in indica rice

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We grew 19 conventional indica rice cultivars in a randomized block design with three replications. Seedlings (32-d-old) were transplanted 2 May 1990 at 16.7- × 13.3-cm spacing. Five plants from each plot were randomly selected at harvest to measure 1,000-grain weight (GW), rough rice length, breadth, length/breadth (L/B) ratio, and HRR.

1. Relationship between grain length and head rice recovery in 19 indica rice cultivars. Hangzhou, China, 1990.

The negative correlation between grain length and HRR was highly significant (Fig. 1), as was the correlation between L/B ratio and HRR (Fig. 2).

2. Relationship between L/B and HRR in 19 indica rice cultivars. Hangzhou, China, 1990.

HRR was inversely associated with length and L/B ratio, but seems not to be associated with GW and breadth. The correlation varied more in grain length and L/B ratio than in GW or breadth.

Pest resistance—diseases

Noncapsid protein (NCP) used for serological assay in indexing rice grassy stunt virus (RGSV)-infected plants

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RGSV-infected plants were found to produce 24 kDa NCP which is common to all tenuiviruses. We prepared antisera against NCP produced by RGSV.

Antiserum from NCP purified by differential pH precipitation and single ultra centrifugation reacted strongly with purified RGSV and infected plants, but not with healthy plants in double antibody sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (DAS-ELISA). This indicates a slight contamination of viral coat protein in NCP preparation. NCP was further purified by sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). The antiserum produced reacted positively with purified NCP and infected plants,

but not with purified RGSV and healthy plants in DAS-ELISA.

Using indirect ELISA greatly increased sensitivity. NCP was detected

Absorbance (405 nm) values for indirect and DAS-ELISA tests during the 24 kDa antiserum purified by SDS-PAGE. The purified NCP, RGSV, and plant sap were adjusted to an initial concentration of 1 mg/ml, $A_{260} = 3.0$, 1 g tissue/ml, respectively.

in purified NCP preparation at a concentration less than 10 ng/ml and in sap from infected plants diluted to 10^{-5} . Sap from healthy rice plants never positively reacted (see figure).

Antiserum produced from a purified NCP obtained from differential pH precipitation can be used to routinely index RGSV-infected plants instead of using RGSV antibody, which is laborious to prepare. Antiserum produced from SDS-PAGE can be used to specifically detect NCP in infected plants.

RGSV-NCP antisera reacted with NCP of rice stripe virus in a double diffusion test, indicating a close relationship between the viruses.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.